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Synthesis of CdS/CoFe₂O₄ nanocomposites by a novel thermal decomposition approach and their use as magnetically separable adsorbent for the removal of toxic dyes

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Introduction: Adsorbents which are magnetic are very useful in the adsorption process due to their easy and rapid magnetic separation after adsorption (1). In order to achieve this goal, combination of metal ferrite nanoparticles and metal sulfide nanoparticles in a nanocomposite has been proposed in the present study. CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles are promising due to their high magneto-crystalline anisotropy, higher coercivity and moderate saturation magnetization compared to other metal ferrite nanoparticles (2). Cadmium sulfide which is a semiconductor (band gap = 2.45 eV) is a valuable candidate for many applications. The reported synthetic methods for the synthesis of CdS/CoFe₂O₄ nanocomposites often require stringent reaction conditions. In order to overcome these limitations, a simple thermal decomposition approach has been proposed in the present study. After characterization, the adsorption efficiency of CdS/CoFe₂O₄ nanocomposites towards the adsorption of rhodamine B (RhB) from an aqueous solution has been tested.

Methods: CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles (CFG-220°C (500)) were first synthesized via glycolate route followed by calcination (3). For the synthesis of nanocomposites, cadmium acetate and thiourea were added to 10 mL diphenyl ether in a 50 mL round bottom flask followed by refluxing in air at 220 °C for 90 min in the presence of CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. Cadmium acetate to thiourea molar ratio was varied as 0.1:0.1, 0.25:0.25 and 0.50:0.50 for the synthesis of nanocomposites CdS/CF (0.10), CdS/CF (0.25) and CdS/CF (0.50), respectively.

Results & Discussion: Powder XRD results indicate the presence of CdS and CoFe₂O₄ phases in the nanocomposites. The intensity of XRD peaks due to CdS increases and that due to CoFe₂O₄ decreases in the nanocomposites as the concentration of precursors (cadmium acetate and thiourea) is increased. EDX results indicate the presence of Cd, S, Co, Fe in the nanocomposites with uniform distribution. TEM image of pure CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles suggests that the sample consists of nanoparticles with mean particle size of 20.3 ± 5.1 nm. In CdS, CdS/CF(0.25) and CdS/CF(0.50) agglomerated nanoparticles with mean particle size of 11.2 ± 1.2 nm, 13.0 ± 2.9 nm and 14.3 ± 3.5 nm, respectively are observed. SAED patterns of the nanocomposites, CdS and CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles indicate their polycrystalline nature. The CdS/CoFe₂O₄ nanocomposites are soft ferrimagnetic and they exhibit lower M_s and M_r compared to pure CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. The nanocomposites show higher adsorption efficiency with higher pseudo second order rate constant and equilibrium adsorption capacity compared to CdS and CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles.

Conclusions: CdS/CoFe₂O₄ nanocomposites were synthesized via a novel thermal decomposition method. XRD, EDX SAED, and TEM results confirm the presence of CdS and CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles in the nanocomposites. The nanocomposites are soft ferrimagnetic and they are promising magnetically separable adsorbent for the adsorption of RhB from an aqueous solution.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, Thermal decomposition method, Magnetically separable adsorbent

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